

PROGRAMMES AND POLICIES FOR POVERTY ALLEVIATION

Dr. Rajesh Pal

Associate Professor

Department of Economics

Mahatma Gandhi Kashi Vidyapith

Varanasi, U.P, India

www.arseam.com

Abstract

Poverty has always been a cause of great concern. Significant decline in poverty ratio has been observed in both rural and urban areas during 2011-12. The rural poverty head count ratio declined by 16 percentage points from 41.8 per cent to 25.7 per cent and urban poverty declined by 12 percentage points from 25.7 per cent to 13.7 per cent. Though, the nation shows considerable improvement in poverty reduction, it is alarming that, still, 1 in every 5 persons in India is below the national poverty line. India's 1.25 billion citizens have higher expectations about their future today, than they have ever had before. In this perspective, this paper discusses various programmes and policies for poverty alleviation. The broad vision and aspirations, which the Twelfth Plan seeks to fulfill are reflected in the subtitle: 'Faster, Sustainable, and More Inclusive Growth'. Inclusive development incorporates social and financial inclusion and in most cases the socially excluded are also financially excluded. The government's policies are directed towards bringing these marginalized sections into the mainstream. Towards this end, the central government has been implementing many social-sector programmes. They can be classified under the following broad heads viz. poverty alleviation and employment generation, social protection, rural infrastructure and development, urban infrastructure, and welfare and development of weaker sections.

Key Words: Poverty, rural, urban, programmes and policies

Introduction

India is one of the world's top producers of rice, wheat, milk, fruits, and vegetables. However, given that India is still home to 1.2 billion people, which is 17 per cent of the world population. In this country of huge diversities, poverty has always been a cause of great concern always. The official poverty estimates released by Planning Commission (Tendulkar methodology) based on NSSO Survey on Household Consumer Expenditure 2011-12 reveals that, the all-India Poverty Head Count Ratio (PHCR) has declined by 15 percentage points from 37.2 per cent in 2004-05 to 21.9 per cent in 2011-12. In absolute terms, the number of poor declined from 407.1 million in 2004-05 to 269.3 million in 2011-12. Significant decline in poverty ratio has been observed in both rural and urban areas during this period. The rural poverty head count ratio declined by 16 percentage points from 41.8 per cent to 25.7 per cent and urban poverty declined by 12 percentage points from 25.7 per cent to 13.7 per cent. Though, the nation shows considerable improvement in poverty reduction, it is alarming that, still, 1 in every 5 persons in India is below the national poverty line. While considering the progress towards millennium development goals (MDG) target 1, the estimate of PHCR at the national level was at 47.8 per cent for 1993 and the country is required to achieve a PHCR level of 23.9 per cent by 2015 in order to meet the MDG target. With a faster decline in PHCR i.e., annual decline of 1.9 percentage points during 2004-12, compared to 0.7 percentage points during 1993-2004, the Country has already achieved the MDG target, which is a notable achievement (Millennium Development Goals India Country Report 2014: 13-14).

India's 1.25 billion citizens have higher expectations about their future today, than they have ever had before. They have seen the economy grow much faster in the past 10 years than it did earlier, and deliver visible benefits to a large number of people. This has understandably raised the expectations of all sections, especially those who have benefited less. India's economic fundamentals have been improving in many dimensions, and this is reflected in the fact that despite the slowdown in 2011-12, the growth rate of the economy averaged 8 per cent in the Eleventh Plan period (XII Five Year Plan, Vol.I:02). This was lower than the Plan target of 9 per cent, but it was better than the achievement of 7.8 per cent in the Tenth Plan. The fact that this growth occurred in a period, which saw two global crises, one in 2008 and another in 2011, is indicative of the resilience, which the economy has developed. In this perspective, this paper discusses various programmes and policies for poverty alleviation. The broad vision and

aspirations, which the Twelfth Plan seeks to fulfil are reflected in the subtitle: ‘Faster, Sustainable, and More Inclusive Growth’. Inclusive development incorporates social and financial inclusion and in most cases the socially excluded are also financially excluded. Many segments of the population like landless agricultural labourers, marginal farmers, scheduled castes (SCs), scheduled tribes (STs), and other backward classes (OBCs) continue to suffer social and financial exclusion. The government’s policies are directed towards bringing these marginalized sections into the mainstream. Towards this end, the central government has been implementing many social-sector programmes (Economic Survey 2013-14: 240). They can be classified under the following broad heads viz. poverty alleviation and employment generation, social protection, rural infrastructure and development, urban infrastructure, and welfare and development of weaker sections.

Poverty Alleviation and Employment Generation Programmes

Some of the major poverty alleviation and employment generation programmes are the following:

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MNREGA): The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MNREGA) is a landmark initiative of the Government of India to address mainly the issue of job guarantee in the rural areas has kept provision for women empowerment also, was enacted on 5th September 2005 and came into force w.e.f. 2nd February 2006. On 31st December 2009, the Act was renamed by an Amendment as the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, 2005. Mahatma Gandhi MNREGA aims at providing not less than 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year to every rural household, with a stipulation of one-third participation of women, through creation of assets that address causes of chronic poverty like drought, deforestation, and soil erosion, thus encouraging sustainable development. With an outlay of Rs. 33,000 crore in 2013-14, the scheme provided 219.72 crore person days of employment to 4.78 crore households with an average wage employment of 46 person days. The share of women, SC, and ST person days in this period was 53 per cent, 23 per cent and 17 per cent respectively. With wages indexed to the consumer price index for agricultural labour (CPI-AL), the average wage under the scheme has increased from Rs. 65 in FY 2006-07 to Rs. 132 in FY 2013-14, resulting in improvement in the bargaining power of agriculture labour. It has also

led to improved economic outcomes, especially in watershed activities, and reduction in distress migration.

National Rural Livelihoods Mission (NRLM) - Aajeevika: The core belief of National Rural Livelihoods Mission (NRLM) is that the poor have innate capabilities and a strong desire to come out of poverty. They are entrepreneurial, an essential coping mechanism to survive under conditions of poverty. Keeping this view in mind, the Ministry of Rural Development has re-designed and re-structured the Swarnjayanti Gram Swarojgar Yojana (SGSY) into National Livelihood Mission (NRLM) as a cornerstone of national poverty reduction strategy. The objective of the Mission is to reduce poverty among rural BPL by promoting diversified and gainful self-employment and wage employment opportunities which that would lead to an appreciable increase in income on sustainable basis. Under this mission women will be provided with information on marketing and business skills including pricing, budgeting, and access to pension and insurance products. The NRLM aims at organizing all rural poor households and continuously nurturing and supporting them till they emerge out of abject poverty, by organizing one woman member from each household into affinity- based women self-help groups (SHGs) and their federations at village and higher levels by 2024-25. The objective is to ensure that each family, once it is in the SHG network for a period of 6-8 years is able to achieve household food security and have 3-4 stabilized livelihoods through a strong convergence with panchayati raj institutions (PRIs). The mission has covered 97,391 villages and mobilized around 20 lakh SHGs, of which 3.8 lakh are new. During 2013-14, Rs. 22121.18 crore of SHG bank credit has been disbursed. For 2014-15, Rs. 3560 crore has been allocated to NRLM. NRLM implementation is in a Mission Mode. As NRLM follows a demand driven strategy, the States have the flexibility to develop their livelihoods-based perspective plans and annual action plans for poverty reduction (Millennium Development Goals: 31). The potential power of the National Rural Livelihoods Mission (NRLM) lies in the economies of scale created by SHG Federations (comprising 150–200 SHGs each). This is evident, for example, in bulk purchase of inputs (seeds, fertilisers and so on) and marketing of outputs (crops, vegetables, milk, NTFPs and so on) (XII Five Year Plan 2012-17, Vol.I: 187).

National Urban Livelihoods Mission (NULM): Swarna Jayanti Shahari Rozgar Yojana (SJSRY) is replaced by the NULM in September 2013 (Economic Survey 2013-14: 240). The National Urban livelihood Mission (NULM) implemented by the Ministry of Housing and Urban Poverty Alleviation aims to reduce poverty and vulnerability of the urban poor households by enabling them to access gainful self employment to urban unemployed and underemployed and skilled wage employment opportunities, resulting in an appreciable improvement in their livelihoods on a sustainable basis, through building strong grassroots level institutions of the poor. The NULM will focus on organizing urban poor in SHGs, creating opportunities for skill development leading to market-based employment, and helping them set up self-employment ventures by ensuring easy access to credit. The mission aims at providing shelter with basic amenities to urban homeless. It also plans to address livelihood concerns of urban street vendors. During 2013-14, Rs. 720.43 crore was released and the number of persons skill trained and assisted for self-employment was 6,83,452 and 1,06,250 respectively. In addition, the mission would also address livelihood concerns of the urban street vendors by facilitating access to suitable spaces, institutional credit, social security and skills to the urban street vendors for accessing emerging market opportunities (Millennium Development Goals: 32).

Social Protection Programmes

Some important social protection programmes are the following:

Aam Aadmi Bima Yojana (AABY): The AABY extends life and disability cover to persons between the ages of 18 and 59 years, living below and marginally above the poverty line in 47 vocational/ occupational groups, including rural landless households. The scheme is also available to all Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY) beneficiaries satisfying eligibility conditions. The AABY provides insurance cover for a sum of Rs. 30,000 on natural death, Rs. 75,000 on death due to accident, Rs. 37,500 on partial permanent disability due to accident, and Rs. 75,000 on death or total permanent disability due to accident. It also provides an add-on benefit of scholarship of Rs. 100 per month per child to a maximum of two children. The total annual premium is Rs. 200 per beneficiary of which 50 per cent comes from the social security fund and the remaining 50 per cent is contributed by the state government/ nodal agency/ beneficiary. A total of 4.61 crore lives are covered under the AABY as on 30 April 2014.

Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY): The RSBY is a smart card-based cashless health insurance scheme, including maternity benefit, provides cover of Rs. 30,000 per annum to each enrolled family, comprising up to five individuals. The beneficiary family pays only Rs.30 per annum as registration/renewal fee. The scheme covers hospitalisation expenses (Out-patient expenses are not covered), including maternity benefit, and pre-existing diseases. The coverage of RSBY was initially limited to the BPL population but was subsequently expanded to other categories. It should be the objective of the Twelfth Plan to use the platform and existing mechanisms of RSBY to cover the entire population below the poverty line (XII Five Year Plan 2012-2017, Vol.III:09). As of now there are about 6.85 crore targeted BPL families and 70.98 lakh reported hospitalization cases. As on 31 March 2014, more than 3.69 crore families were covered under the RSBY. During 2013-14, Rs. 885.91 crore was released. The benefits of RSBY are being extended to all unorganized workers in a phased manner.

The Unorganized Workers Social Security Act 2008 and National Social Security Fund:

The Act provides for constitution of a National Social Security Board and State Social Security Boards that will recommend social security schemes for unorganized workers. A National Social Security Fund with initial allocation of Rs. 1000 crore to support social security schemes for weavers, toddy tappers, rickshaw pullers, beedi workers, etc. has also been set up. Further, Rs. 500 crore has been added to the fund.

Rural Infrastructure and Development Programmes

Rural infrastructure and development programmes have been designed to achieve a higher degree of rural-urban integration and an even pattern of growth and opportunities for the poor and disadvantaged sections of society. Some such programmes are the following:

Indira Awaas Yojana (IAY): Indira Awaas Yojana (IAY) is a centrally sponsored scheme for rural BPL families who are either houseless or having inadequate housing facilities for constructing a safe and durable shelter. The IAY aims at providing dwelling units to houseless below poverty line (BPL) households identified by the gram sabhas and those living in dilapidated and kutcha houses, with a component for providing house sites to the landless poor as well. Under the IAY, 95 per cent of the total budget would be utilized for the components

relating to new houses, up-gradation of houses and provision of house sites and administrative expenses. The remaining 5 per cent would be reserved for special projects of rehabilitation of BPL families affected by natural calamities, violence, law and order problems, and Settlement of freed bonded labourers and liberated manual scavengers (Millennium Development Goals: 30). Shelterless BPL family would be given assistance of Rs. 70,000 in plains areas and Rs. 75,000 in hilly/difficult areas/Integrated Action Plan (IAP) districts for construction of a new house. For up-gradation of kutchha or dilapidated houses, Rs. 15,000 is provided. For purchase of house sites, Rs. 20,000 is provided. The physical target for construction during 2013-14 is 24.81 lakh houses, of which 10.93 lakh have been constructed and 23.76 lakh are under construction. During 2013-14, a total of Rs. 13,894.90 crore was allocated for construction of 24.81 lakh houses and Rs. 12,970 crore was released. Under the Indira Awas Yojana, funds are allocated State-wise based upon the housing shortage and population below the poverty line. Consequently in 2010–11, Bihar received about 25 per cent of the allocation under the programme. Similarly, in the case of the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM), 17 States have been identified for focused attention (XII Five Year Plan 2012-2017, Vol.I:320).

Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY): Empowering rural India through the strategic provision of all-season road access has emerged as one of the key priorities for the Government of India. The main mechanism for enhancing rural connectivity in a more systematic way has been the Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY), a Centrally Sponsored Scheme (CSS), launched on the 25 December 2000 with the objective of providing all-weather road connectivity to all eligible unconnected habitations in rural areas of the country having population of 500 persons and above in plains areas and 250 persons and above (as per the 2001 census) in special category states, selected tribal and desert areas.. (XII Five Year Plan 2012-2017, Vol.III:218-219). It also permits up-gradation of existing rural roads. Since inception, projects for providing new connectivity to 1,44,717 habitations with a road length of 5,44,462 km have been cleared at an estimated cost of Rs. 1,82,560 crore including up-gradation. A total of 3,99,979 km road length has been completed and new connectivity has been provided to over 97,838 habitations up to March 2014. During 2013-14, 25,316 km of all-weather road including new connectivity to 6560 habitations has been completed at an expenditure of Rs. 13,095 crore. Up-gradation of selected existing roads has also been taken up. The PMGSY will be engendered by incorporating gender differentials and women-specific needs especially in

keeping with women's economic, domestic and community management roles. The ongoing process of convergence between PMGSY and MGNREGA will be strengthened by strategic coordination with NRLM aimed at the empowerment of women (XII Five Year Plan 2012-2017, Vol.III:177).

National Rural Drinking Water Programme (NRDWP): Provision of safe drinking water is a basic necessity. Water is a State subject and rural water supply has been included in the Eleventh Schedule of the Constitution among the subjects that may be entrusted to Panchayats by the States. Considering the magnitude of the problem, the Central Government has been supplementing the efforts of the State Governments through the centrally sponsored Accelerated Rural Water Supply Programme (ARWSP) since 1972-73 (Millennium Development Goals: 143-150). Women will be actively involved in determining the location of sanitation facilities. Targets will be set for providing toilets with water in all schools and anganwadi centres. Under the NRDWP, the goal is to ensure that every rural person in the country has access to 70 litre of water per capita per day (lpcd) within their household premises or at a distance of not more than 50 m by 2022. The coverage under the programme is 68 per cent. However, slippages happen owing to depleting groundwater levels, increase in population, demand for increased levels of service, and low involvement of gram panchayats and communities in the planning, implementation and monitoring. Increasing contamination of drinking water sources for a variety of reasons is another problem. As on March 2014, about 73.8 per cent of rural habitations are fully covered with the provision of at least 40 lpcd of safe drinking water. The rest are either partially covered or have chemical contamination in drinking water sources. During 2013-14, a target to cover 1,41,838 habitations was fixed against which coverage of 1,52,423 habitations has been reported. The outlay for rural drinking water supply has been increased from Rs. 4098 crore in 2005-06 to Rs. 9700 crore in 2013-14. According to the NSS 69th round (Key Indicators on Drinking Water, July 2012 to December 2012) there were 88.5 per cent estimated rural households in India with access to drinking water from improved sources and 11.5 per cent with access to drinking water from unimproved sources. However, Census 2011 reported that 84.2 per cent of rural households (Economic Survey 2013-14, 242) have access to improved drinking water sources from taps, hand pumps, and covered wells.

Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan (NBA): Individual Health and hygiene is largely dependent on adequate availability of drinking water and proper sanitation. There is, therefore, a direct relationship between water, sanitation and health. Government started the Central Rural Sanitation Programme (CRSP) in 1986 primarily with the objective of improving the quality of life of the rural people and to provide privacy and dignity to women. Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan (NBA) envisages covering the entire community for saturated outcomes with a view to create Nirmal Gram Panchayats. The strategy of NBA is to transform rural India into 'Nirmal Bharat' by adopting the 'community led' and 'people centred' strategies and community saturation approach. A "demand driven approach" is to be continued with emphasis on awareness creation and demand generation for sanitary facilities in houses, schools, and for cleaner environment (Millennium Development Goals: 147-149).

According to Census 2011, only 32.7 per cent of rural households have latrine facilities. The NBA, started in 2012, aims at achieving 100 per cent access to sanitation for all households by 2022. As of today, NBA projects have been sanctioned in 607 districts with a total outlay of Rs. 22,672 crore, of which the central share is Rs. 14,888 crore. Allocation for the NBA has increased from Rs. 1500 crore in 2011-12 (Revised Estimates) to Rs. 2300 crore in 2013-14 (Revised Estimates). The provision of incentives for individual household latrine units has been widened to cover above poverty line (APL) households belonging to SCs, STs, and other vulnerable sections along with all BPL households. The number of households being provided toilets annually has increased from 6.21 lakh in 2002-03 to 45 lakh in 2012-13. During 2013-14 (up to March 2014), over 49 lakh toilets were provided to households.

Backward Regions Grant Fund (BRGF): The most important intervention of the Central Government is the special area development programmes that have a clear focus on some aspect of development in identified backward areas. One of these programmes is BRGF. The BRGF was launched in late 2006 at the end of the Tenth Plan, was designed to redress regional imbalances in development. It aimed at catalysing development in backward areas by converging, through supplementary infrastructure and capacity building, the substantial existing development inflows into these districts as part of a well conceived, participatory district plan (XII Five Year Plan 2012-2017, Vol.I:320). The BRGF programme is now applicable in 272 identified backward districts of 27 states, except Goa. The untied funds under the BRGF provide financial resources for supplementing and converging existing development inflows and bridging

the critical gaps in local infrastructure and other development requirements that are not being adequately met through other sources of funding. The planning is participatory in nature by Panchayati Raj Institutions with a bottom-up approach.

Urban Infrastructure Programmes

The following are major initiatives for providing better urban infrastructure, housing, and sanitation facilities:

Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission (JNNURM): The JNNURM launched in December 2005 is being implemented in cities with focus on up-gradation of urban infrastructure, encourage reforms and fast track planned development of identified cities, creation of housing stock, and provision of basic services to the poor through community participation and accountability of urban local bodies. In addition to improving the basic amenities and infrastructure in urban areas, the programme also targets to improve the conditions of slums. The mission is implemented through (a) the Basic Services to the Urban Poor (BSUP) programme, and (b) the Integrated Housing and Slum Development Programme (IHSDP). The BSUP is applicable to 65 select cities in the country and the remaining cities are covered under the IHSDP. Under the BSUP, 519 projects at a total cost of Rs. 28,569.9 crore for the construction of 9,68,486 dwelling units (DUs) have been approved. Under the IHSDP, 1070 projects for construction of 5,52,288 DUs in 910 cities have been approved at a total cost of Rs. 11,681.51 crore . As on 31 March 2014, 8,03,453 houses have been constructed and 5,80,030 houses occupied by beneficiaries. Out of Rs. 21,594.83 crore additional central assistance for these projects, Rs. 17,117.99 crore has been disbursed to states.

Rajiv Awaas Yojana (RAY): The Rajiv Awas Yojana envisages a “Slum Free India” with inclusive and equitable cities in which every citizen has access to basic civic infrastructure, social amenities and decent shelter, was launched in 2011 and 54 pilot projects and 228 cities have been included under the preparatory phase of programme with total project cost of Rs. 2468.51 crore of which the central share is (Economic Survey 2013-14, 243) Rs. 1361.84 crore. As a part of promoting economic opportunities for women in urban slum areas, particularly if the settlements are away from the city, space and buildings will be allotted for creation of work

sheds for women in Rajiv Awas Yojana settlements (XII Five Year Plan 2012-2017, Vol.III:178). In the implementation phase, 112 projects for construction/up-gradation of 78,664 DUs, at a total project cost of Rs. 4003.55 crore of which the central share is Rs. 2169.35 crore, have been sanctioned. This programme addresses some of the causes leading to creation of slums. The objectives of the programme are:

- Empowering community by ensuring their participation at every stage of decision making through strengthening and nurturing Slum Dwellers' Association/Federation.
- Improving and provisioning of housing, basic civic infrastructure and social amenities in intervened slums, and
- Facilitating a supportive environment for expanding institutional credit linkages for the urban poor (Millennium Development Goals: 33).

The scheme is applicable to all slums within a city, whether notified or non-notified. It is also applicable to “urbanized villages” inside the planning area of the city, urban homeless and pavement dwellers.

Welfare and Development Programmes for Weaker Sections

Economic and social empowerment along with educational upliftment of socially disadvantaged groups and marginalized sections of society can help in achieving faster and more inclusive (Economic Survey 2013-14,250) development. An amount of Rs. 5084.56 crore has been released for social justice and empowerment during 2013-14. Some schemes targeted at the different weaker sections are as follows:

Scheduled Castes (SCs)

- **Special Central Assistance (SCA) to the Schedule Castes Sub Plan (SCSP):** The persistence of socio-economic backwardness of the SCs and the STs in spite of the development efforts had warranted a special and focused strategy, inter alia, to enable them to share the benefits of overall economic growth in a more equitable manner. This has been sought to be achieved through the Special Component Plan (SCP) for Scheduled Castes, now known as Scheduled Caste Sub Plan (SCSP) and the Tribal Sub-Plan for Scheduled Tribes. The prime objective of Scheduled Caste Sub Plan (SCSP) is to channelise funds and benefits through identified schemes, for which the States/UTs and

Union Ministries have to earmark funds in proportion to the SC population in the State/UTs and the country respectively (XII Five Year Plan 2012-2017, Vol.III:244). This aims at uplifting the SCs above the poverty line through self-employment or skill development for which subsidy is provided. During 2013-14, Rs. 790.25 crore has been released to the states for an estimated 6.08 lakh beneficiaries. Several legislations have been enacted for securing the civil rights of SCs and STs. For providing support to SCs, Rs. 3990.14 crore has been released during 2013-14.

- **Scholarship Schemes:** Pre-matric scholarships have been introduced in 2012, for classes IX and X for SC children so as to minimize the incidence of drop-out, especially in the transition from elementary to secondary stage. An amount of Rs. 547.17 crore was released to the states during 2013-14 for an estimated 19.10 lakh beneficiaries for the purpose. Under the Post-matric Scholarship Scheme for SCs, central assistance of Rs. 2153 crore was released to the states during 2013-14 for 52.78 lakh beneficiaries.
- **Other Schemes:** There are other schemes for SC students like the Rajiv Gandhi National Fellowship Scheme which aims at providing financial assistance to SC students pursuing M Phil and Ph D courses, National Overseas Scholarship Scheme which provides financial support to students pursuing Master's level and PhD/post-doctoral courses abroad, and the Top Class Education Scheme which provides full financial support to eligible students who secure admission in notified premier institutions like the Indian Institutes of Technology (IIT), Indian Institutes of Management (IIM), and National Institutes of Technology (NIT).

Scheduled Tribes (STs)

Various policies and programmatic and legislative interventions have been made for the socio-economic development and empowerment of the STs. As per Planning Commission (2009- 10), 47.4 per cent of STs in rural areas and 30.4 per cent in urban areas were below the poverty line. Major schemes targeted at their welfare are as follows:

- **Tribal Sub Plan and Special Area Programmes:** The Tribal Sub-Plan (TSP) is an instrument for accelerating socio-economic development by bridging the developmental gaps between STs and the general population. The prime object of the Tribal Sub Plan is

development of tribal areas. The TSP concept, thus, aims on one hand, at the quantification of investment in the Sub-Plan areas commensurate with its size and on the other, at an all-round development of the tribal communities, in accordance with their needs (XII Five Year Plan 2012-2017, Vol.III:245). During 2013-14, Rs. 3879 crore (Revised Estimates) was allocated for the welfare and development of STs. Major expenditure was incurred on central assistance to state governments under two special area programmes, (i) grants to states to supplement their TSP (SCA to TSP) for income generating schemes, creation of incidental infrastructure, community based activities and development of forest villages, and (ii) grants under article 275(I) of the constitution for development and up-gradation of administration in tribal areas. The latter is also used for setting up of Eklavya Model Residential Schools (EMRS) in states for providing quality education in remote areas. The revised allocation under these two programmes was Rs. 2147.14 crore during 2013-14, which has been released to the states.

- **Economic Empowerment Programmes:** For economic empowerment of STs, financial support is extended through the National Scheduled Tribes Finance and Development Corporation (NSTFDC) in the form of loans and micro-credit at concessional rates of interest for income-generating activities. During 2013-14, the corporation disbursed Rs. 141.35 crore for various income-generation activities of STs. Forward linkage is provided by the Tribal Cooperative Marketing Development Federation of India (TRIFED). A new scheme was launched in 2013-14 as a mechanism for marketing of minor forest produce through minimum support price and development of value chain, for which Rs. 112.49 crore was released to state implementing agencies.
- **Educational Development Programmes:** Despite continued support by the government, low educational levels among STs remain an area of concern. To address this issue, a Pre-matric Scholarship scheme launched in July 2012 provides 100 per cent financial assistance. The Post-matric Scholarship scheme also provides 100 per cent financial assistance. The Top Class Education Scheme provides financial assistance for quality education to 625 students per annum for pursuing Master's and doctoral and post-doctoral studies in identified institutes. Under the pre-matric scheme and post-matric scheme Rs. 219.43 crore and Rs. 748.45 crore respectively have been released in 2013-14.

Minorities

For the development of minorities, the plan outlay was raised from Rs. 3135 crore in 2012-13 to Rs. 3511 crore in 2013-14. Three scholarships schemes, namely Pre-matric, Post-matric and Merit-cum-Means based, were implemented exclusively for the notified minorities with a total provision of Rs. 1770 crore in 2013-14. The Multi-sectoral Development Programme, is a special area development initiative to address the 'development deficits' especially in education, skill development, employment, health and sanitation, housing, and drinking water in 196 minority concentration districts under which projects worth Rs. 1466.98 Crore were approved during 2013-14. The corpus of the Maulana Azad Education Foundation has been enhanced from Rs. 100 crore in 2005-06 to Rs. 910 crore up to March 2014 and will be further enhanced by Rs. 113 crore during 2014-15 for expanding its activities. There are also special programmes to benefit other backward classes (OBCs) and persons with disabilities. (Economic Survey 2013-14: 251)

Conclusion

Strengthening the agri-sector and development of rural and urban infrastructure is crucial for poverty alleviation, ensuring food security, increasing employment opportunities, and enhancing rural incomes. Further, with 10.4 per cent of total households in rural areas being headed by a woman (Census 2011), it is essential to formulate policies, and package technologies and services keeping in view the productive role played by women in all facets of the agri-sector. Experience from BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) countries indicates that a 1 per cent growth in agriculture is at least two to three times more effective in reducing poverty than the same growth emanating from non-agriculture sectors.

References

Economic Survey (2013-14), Government of India, New Delhi

Millennium Development Goals India Country Report, 2014, Social Statistics Division, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India, www.mospi.nic.in.

XII Five Year Plan (2012-2017), Planning Commission, Government of India, New Delhi.